

Facial Recognition System for Ethnicity Classification with Regional Convolutional Neural Network

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Abstract:

In recent times, a facial recognition system is described as a form of technology that is capable of matching a human face from a set of digital images or a video frame against a database of faces, this is mostly used to authenticate a user's ID verification in workplaces by the analytical measure of facial features from the set of input images. One of its drawbacks is that it tends to allow for the invasion of privacy, misuse of power, and rogue intrusion in government parastatals but these drawbacks don't render it from being in the spotlight and its investments have skyrocketed. This paper talks about the design of a novel facial recognition system (Facial-Cognizant) that uses a parallel multifarious search process to search for an identity in the database and also from the static image capture from a real-time video sequence, the features, and cascaded object detector is used based on Regional Convolution Neural Network (R-CNN) with a simple computational method to identify the best fit to the input image. The procedures and result is discussed in the proceeding sections.

Keywords: Regional Convolution Neural Network, User Authentication, Image capture, Facial recognition system, Object detection, Multifarious effect

1 Introduction

The development of facial recognition systems began in the early 60s, with the initial stage as a form of computer application. In the early days of development, their inception has seen wider users which impact recent times on smartphones and other forms of technology, including robotics. The modernization of the facial recognition system embeds human physiological characteristics and is categorized as real-time biometrics [Persiani et al. (2021); Dargan and Kumar (2020); Mohsin et al. (2018); Shaheed et al. (2021); Alsaadi (2015); Agrafioti et al. (2011)]. The accuracy of facial recognition systems as modified biometrics is relatively low compared to iris recognition systems and fingerprint recognition due to different variations in facial features. It is also widely adopted due to its unified contactless procedures. The systems have been deployed in the most advanced human-computer interaction series such as automatic video indexing, video camera surveillance, and other automobile sectors.

The facial recognition system is employed in worldwide government and private sectors. Its effectiveness differs and some of these systems have previously been scrapped due to ineffectiveness. The main purpose of these systems has

raised controversy violating citizens' privacy and the habit of making wrong detection and facial identification on gender norms and racial photo profiling [Scheuerman et al. (2020); Buolamwini and Gebru (2018); Wang and Kosinski (2018); Khan et al. (2019); Hung and Carpenter (2017); Hung et al. (2020)], sometimes it does protect important biometric data. These set claims have led to the scrapping of facial recognition systems in some countries. To contribute to some of these drawbacks, the paper highlights a novel method of facial recognition by proposing a multifarious image search using R-CNN on an image or ID search for a particular individual [Fast (2018); Liu et al. (2020); Jiang et al. (2022); Li et al. (2017)].

The rationale for using the R-CNN is to take an input image and produce a set of bounding boxes as output, where each bounding box contains an object and also the category of the object from a set of databases, for the case in the parallel set, only three images are allowed for the best fit for images close to the input image matrix and. This process used a set length L_{loc} for its location for a set of input images in the parallel reduction module (Equations 1 and 2), where t and v are the time and distance from every smooth search. More recently [Vecvanags et al. (2022); Ball et al. (2023); Majid and Smith (2019); Rane (2023)], R-CNN has been extended to perform other computational tasks such as user demography information and a system performance check for authentication of the summary information about an individual. The following covers some of the versions of R-CNN that have been developed

$$L_{loc}(t^u, v) = \sum_{i \in \{x, y, w, h\}}^n \text{smooth}_{L_1}(t_1 - v_i),$$

$$\text{where } \text{smooth}_{L_1}(x) = \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} 0.5x^2 & \text{if } |x| \leq 1 \\ |x| - 0.5 & \text{otherwise} \end{array} \right\} \quad (1)$$

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \downarrow x_m = 2x_{out} + 1 \\ \text{Reduction module} \rightarrow m \\ \downarrow x_{out} \end{array} \right\} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \downarrow x_{m0} = 2x_{m-1} + 1 \\ \text{Reduction module} \\ \downarrow x_{m-1} = 2x_{m-2} + 1 \\ \text{Reduction module}(m-1) \downarrow \\ \vdots \\ \downarrow x_1 = 2x_0 + 1 \\ \text{Reduction module} \\ \downarrow x_0 \\ \rightarrow x_m = 2^m x_0 + 2^m 2(m \in M) \end{array} \right\} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{x_m+1}{x_{m-1}+1} = 2 \\ \frac{x_{m-1}+1}{x_{m-2}+1} = 2 \\ \vdots \\ \frac{x_1+1}{x_0+1} = 2 \end{array} \right\} \quad (2)$$

The example of the system design in this paper shows how to automatically detect and track facial features using the main feature points like the eyes, nose, mouth, and side detection. The approach in this paper keeps track of the face even when the person tilts his or her head or moves toward or away from the camera lens

2 Method

In image processing, object detection and tracking are very important in many computer vision and applications which includes activities recognized in certain patterns, this also includes surveillance and automotive safety. In this section a method is adopted in developing a complex facial recognition and tracking system by dividing the tracking problem into three (3) parts, this includes:

- a reduction module that detects the eyes, nose, and mouth features, identifies the side facial features to track the face in a single module and then detects a face.
- to detect the face using the R-CNN vision cascade object detector on the location of the features that make up the face in the static or real-time image created from the video frame.
- object detector trains the classifier model for detection. The default for the app is configured to detect faces only and a subsequent version will be trained to detect other forms of objects. Face can also be tracked over time. This is a less expensive method since it uses a low memory size (250Mb) and a higher illumination-powered mobile lens on Android systems.

The feature points identified by the vision point tracker in the module are used as the object classifier to track the main features that make up a face. Each point in each frame allows for a point tracker that attempts to find the corresponding point in the current frame and map the resultant search to the best fit in the database from a list of three likely matches. The name and ID from the user demography can also be used to trace similar and identical results based on the given information. The R-CNN is implemented using five (5) different epochs on the search from the database of images (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Framework for R-CNN using five different epochs on the Database of images

3 Result

Figure 2 shows the interface used for the proposed model, the initial stage is taking an input image that is located and registered in the database, its demography loads in when the person’s information is available online. A black profile is loaded if no demography is seen. Once a face is detected among the best possible match the result is displayed. If the same features are detected again in a search with different inputs, the system will indicate how many faces are in the image and the individuals with the detected faces. The database contains different images from an online survey and locally included real-time images from a mobile app. Background images are usually filtered out because they are considered anomalies by the inference engine.

Figure 2: Window form with image match in parallel face recognition set.

The print icon in Figure 2 is set on a module that displays the information on the best fit and corresponding demography. This information about the individual is sometimes entered manually for system testing in the database. The initial state is also considered close to 100 images, subjecting the system to a minimum processing speed due to the memory size which is a bit low for the window form. Figure 3 shows the interface for the best match with user information. The physiological metrics involve the pupil changes measured in real-time during the process of tracking for a static point to capture the images and detected features that match the input image. Since some of the information in the database is manually entered, the search field can contain the name of the person and eye color, and this selects the best match based on the text input. This is also a single module in the system that uses a natural language process to match the name to any search pattern in the database. The biometric automatically records pupil changes (dilation and constriction) and the eye color which are embedded as part of the information about the individual.

Figure 3: Window form with image match in parallel face recognition set.

To evaluate the performance of the proposed face recognition model in terms of image capture, a list of self-captured facial images was used in the analysis stage. The recognition and tracking pattern for different facial expressions and poses were measured using Tracker operating characteristics (TOC). The recognition rate is the ratio of the successfully matched images i.e. cases where the best match is the correct match to the total attempts. Figure 4 below shows the result for the five different R-CNN with different epochs. The result shows that the first and the third epoch have a correction rate of 98% and 3%. This makes the multifarious technique very robust and suitable for other applications.

4 Conclusion

This paper set out to investigate a designed facial recognition system (Facial-Cognizant) a multifarious facial recognition system for ethnicity classification with R-CNN. The procedure follows a simple but composite facial recognition system was created which involves tracking and automatically detecting a single face among a list of likely matches. Other patterns were tested to see if the system could detect and track a face similar to its inputs in terms of text and image input. The demographic information about the person is produced and gives a similar output to the input image. The estimated geometric transformation from the model is used to estimate the motion of the face for a static profile captured. Physiological metrics are also applied to capture the cognitive state of the individual and are embedded as part of the person's demography information. The system performance on different epochs shows high performance in terms of a perfect match for the five epochs used in the model and this makes the system make generalized and adaptive to other applications. The future perspective would be to compare the performance of the system to other learning models such as SVM, Fast R-CNN, and Decision Tree for system optimization and modifications.

Figure 4: ROC curve results for the five different R-CNN with different epochs.

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